

CODEBOOK

Dataset title: Survey Dataset on Students' Personal Financial Management Education Assessment, Portfolio Risk and Future investment prospects, 2025

Variables Descriptions

Variable name	Description	Type	Values/ coding
Gender	Gender of respondent	Categorical	1=female, 2=male
Age range	Age of respondent	Categorical	1=less than 20, 2=less than 30, 3=less than 40
Origin	Background of the respondent	Categorical	1=African, 2=Asian, 3=European, 4=Australian, 5=others
Field of study	Respondent's academic focus	categorical	1=Agriculture and geography related, 2=Arts related, 3=Business & Accounting related, 4=Medical, technology and science, 5=others
Personal Financial Management Education	All column heads denoted by PFME	Scale	1=very low – 5=very high
Portfolio Risk	All column heads denoted by PR	Scale	1=very low – 5=very high
Level of Financial Literacy	All column heads denoted by LFL	Scale	1=very low – 5=very high
Minimum Investment Capital	All column heads denoted by MIC	Scale	1=very low – 5=very high
Projection of Future Investments	All column heads denoted by PFI	Scale	1=very low – 5=very high
Financial Discipline	All column heads denoted as FD	Scale	1=very low – 5=very high